

REPORT #11

Evolution of educational equity and school segregation in Ireland

Assessment and promotion of educational equity in secondary education: secondary análisis of PISA and training of key educational agents (Evaluación y promoción de la equidad Educativa en educación sEcundaria: Análisis secundario de las evaluaciones PISA y formación de agentes educativos clave)

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Table of contents

EVIDENCE project: phase one	3
National project R+D 2021 (Spain) EVIDENCE.....	3
Phase one: evolution of educational equity	3
Interpretation of equity indicators	4
Indicators for equity as equal achievement.....	4
Indicators for equity as equal opportunities.....	5
Evolution of equity indicators in the country	6
Evolution of equity as equal achievement.....	6
Evolution of equity as equal opportunities.....	8
Global score of the indicators	11

EVIDENCE project: phase one

National project R+D 2021 (Spain) EVIDENCE

EVIDENCE is a research and development project (2021 project call, reference PID2021-125775NB-I00) granted by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and coordinated by the Educational Assessment and Guidance Research Group (GE2O), which is integrated in the Research Group of Interaction and E-Learning (GRIAL) of the University Institute for Educational Sciences (IUCE, Universidad de Salamanca).

The aim of this project is:

To study de evolution of educational equity levels in secondary education and to promote the main educational protective factors.

This aim will be achieved in three phases, presented in chronological order:

1. **Study of the evolution of educational equity in secondary education** from PISA data (2000-2018) under two approaches:
 - a. Equity as equal achievement. Evolution of achievement variability in a country or region.
 - b. Equity as equal opportunities. Progress of the relationship between a measure of family socioeconomic level (SES) and achievement, both at student and school levels; and evolution of school segregation, defined as the variability of SES at school level.
2. **Identification of educational factors that promote educational equity**, from the analysis of PISA 2018 and 2022 waves.
3. **Design, implementation and assessment of training programmes on educational equity** aimed at school heads, guidance counsellors and key actors in secondary education.

Phase one: evolution of educational equity

Within phase one of the Project, this report presents indicators for educational equity and school segregation obtained in Ireland. In order to facilitate a comparative analysis, the results of each indicator will be accompanied by the average of European countries (EU members) and the average of the OECD countries to act as a baseline.

As a member of the Project in Ireland, once you receive the report you will be asked to:

Analyse the evolution of educational equity in your country and consider the possible influence of changes in socioeconomic conditions and socio-educational policies on this evolution.

Interpretation of equity indicators

An education system should strive not just to reach high competence or achievement levels, but also acceptable and generalized achievement levels in most students and schools (equal achievement) and to ensure the same access to education (equal opportunities):

Indicators for equity as equal achievement

INDICATOR	LEVEL	UNIT	FORMULA	EXPLANATION
Variation Coefficient (CV)	Student	Percentage (%)	$CV (\%) = \frac{S_x}{ \bar{x} } * 100$	<p>CV indicates how disperse or heterogeneous the values of a variable are (in this case the variable is student achievement). A CV=0% indicates that all students or schools have obtained exactly the same achievement level. The indicator at student level refers to the differences in achievement among the students of a country, and the indicator at school level refers to the differences among the schools' average scores.</p> <p>In order to interpret this indicator, you can use the following reference points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CV=20% → Average achievement differences • CV<20% → Achievement differences below average • CV>20% → Achievement differences above average <p>In an education system, differences in student achievement (CV at student level) are to be expected, but a high CV at school level would indicate that there are schools with vastly different average scores, which would violate the principle of equity as equal achievement.</p>
	School			
ICC of achievement	School	Percentage (%)	$Rend_{ij} = \gamma_{00} + u_{0j} + e_{ij}$ $Ineq_{ir} = \frac{\sigma_j^2}{\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2}$ <p>*Rend= achievement Ineq_{ir} = ICC_{achievement} Subindex <i>i</i> is for student Subindex <i>j</i> is for school</p>	<p>ICC_{achievement} indicates the percentage of the total variance of the achievement of a country's students ($\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2$) that can be explained by the grouping of students in schools (σ_j^2 or between school variability), considering σ_i^2 as the variability of students within a school (within school variability).</p> <p>In order to interpret this indicator, you can use the following reference points:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICC<20% → The average achievement of schools is very similar, there is a low achievement inequality due to the grouping of students in schools • ICC>60% → The average achievement of schools is very different, the grouping of students in schools is highly unequal <p>A country with similar schools according to its achievement levels (low ICC) is equitable: this indicates that there is no student segregation based on achievement. On the contrary, high levels of ICC indicate that students are highly segregated based on their achievement, and this promotes inequality.</p>

Indicators for equity as equal opportunities

INDICATOR	LEVEL	UNIT	FORMULA	EXPLANATION
Pearson's correlation (R_{xy})	Student	Score ranging from (-1 , 1)	$R_{xy} = \frac{S_{xy}}{S_x * S_y}$ <p>* Y= Achievement X= Socioeconomic level</p>	<p>This correlation indicates the type and intensity of the relationship between two variables: achievement and socioeconomic status (SES). A value of $R_{xy}=0$ indicates that achievement and SES are independent, therefore the country is equitable.</p> <p>R_{xy} at student level indicates the relationship between the two variables in all the students from a country. R_{xy} at school level indicates the relationship between all the schools' average achievement and average SES.</p> <p>At student level, the indicator can be interpreted as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $R_{xy} < 0.30 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a small relationship $R_{xy} > 0.45 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a large relationship <p>At school level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $R_{xy} < 0.40 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a small relationship $R_{xy} > 0.80 \rightarrow$ SES and achievement have a large relationship <p>There is a clear and direct R_{xy} between these two variables at an international level (high-SES students have higher achievements and vice versa), which is a relevant source of inequity: favourable socioeconomic conditions facilitate a greater academic success, thus limiting the equitable access to education and hindering the social promotion that an education system should promote.</p>
	School			
ICC of SES	School	Percentage (%)	$NSE_{ij} = \gamma_{00} + u_{0j} + e_{ij}$ $Segr. = \frac{\sigma_j^2}{\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2}$ <p>*NSE=SES Segregation. = ICC_{SES} Subindex i is for student Subindex j is for school</p>	<p>ICC_{NSE} indicates the percentage of the total variance of the SES of a country's students ($\sigma_j^2 + \sigma_i^2$) that can be explained by the grouping of students in schools (σ_j^2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICC<20% \rightarrow The average achievement of schools is very similar, there is a low achievement inequality due to the grouping of students in schools ICC>45% \rightarrow The average achievement of schools is very different, the grouping of students in schools is highly inequal <p>A country where schools have similar average SES (low ICC) is equitable: there is no segregation of students based on their SES. A high ICC indicates inequity due to socioeconomic segregation.</p>
School inequity (SI)	School and student	Percentage (%)	$inequ. = \frac{\sigma_{jnull}^2 - \sigma_{jfinal}^2}{\sigma_{jnull}^2}$ <p>* Inequ. = IE Subindex j is for school</p>	<p>School Inequity (SI) indicates the percentage of the total variability of achievement at school level which can be explained by SES, that is, the impact of SES in a country's achievement. In a country with a high SI, low-SES students have many difficulties in order to access education and to benefit from social promotion through education. This indicator can be interpreted as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> SI<25% \rightarrow Low SES does not hinder an equitable access to education SI>55% \rightarrow Low SES hinders an equitable access to education <p>This is the main indicator of equity as equal opportunities in a country, since it encompasses the partial information shown by both R_{xy} scores mentioned above.</p>

Evolution of equity indicators in the country

Below you will find the results obtained in Ireland, both in terms of the country's evolution as well as a comparison of said evolution against the average of European countries and OECD members.

Evolution of equity as equal achievement

Table 1 provides data of the indicators that explore the variability of achievement in the education system, both at student and school level.

Table 1. Evolution of equity as equal achievement indicators

		2000	2003	2006	2009	2012	2015	2018
CV_{student}	Ireland	16,44%	16,36%	16,73%	17,91%	16,33%	15,91%	16,06%
	EU	19,14%	18,04%	18,19%	18,15%	17,89%	18,37%	18,38%
	OECD	18,56%	18,22%	18,23%	17,84%	17,91%	18,10%	18,29%
CV_{school}	Ireland	8,04%	9,26%	9,11%	9,94%	8,99%	7,85%	7,96%
	EU	15,49%	13,51%	13,75%	13,51%	13,78%	13,09%	13,66%
	OECD	14,50%	13,36%	13,64%	13,06%	13,47%	12,50%	13,15%
ICC_{achievement}	Ireland	20,65%	23,96%	22,54%	25,60%	24,53%	18,40%	18,16%
	EU	47,54%	42,65%	46,01%	45,59%	46,54%	41,50%	42,57%
	OECD	44,42%	39,74%	42,57%	42,16%	42,91%	38,11%	39,09%

Graph 1 shows that the variation coefficient for students in Ireland has maintained a rather stable evolution (except for a slight peak in 2009), keeping below EU and OECD levels.

Graph 1. Evolution of the variation coefficient (CV) at student level

Graph 2 shows a similar picture for the variation coefficient at school level, although the distance with EU and OECD levels is larger. Ireland's score in the indicator goes from 8% in 2000 to 10% in 2009 (the highest value), but it goes back down to 8% over the course of the next 9 years.

Graph 2. Evolution of the variation coefficient (CV) at school level

Graph 3 show a non-linear evolution of inequity measured as unequal distribution of achievement at school level, with the indicator going up from 20% to 25% (2009) and descending below 20% in 2015 and 2018, well below EU and OECD averages.

Graph 3. Evolution of ICC achievement (school inequity due to unequal achievement distribution)

Evolution of equity as equal opportunities

Table 2 provides data on all indicators related to equal opportunities in education, assessed mainly through the relationship between SES and achievement at student and school levels (School Inequity).

Table 2. Evolution of equity as equal opportunities indicators

		2000	2003	2006	2009	2012	2015	2018
Rxy_{student}	Ireland	0,34	0,44	0,38	0,37	0,40	0,38	0,35
	EU	0,39	0,44	0,40	0,40	0,41	0,39	0,39
	OECD	0,39	0,43	0,39	0,40	0,39	0,37	0,38
Rxy_{school}	Ireland	0,71	0,87	0,80	0,69	0,82	0,79	0,84
	EU	0,64	0,70	0,66	0,66	0,69	0,68	0,67
	OECD	0,64	0,71	0,66	0,66	0,67	0,65	0,65
ICC_{SES}	Ireland	21,06%	24,48%	24,40%	27,16%	24,04%	20,97%	20,26%
	EU	31,27%	29,40%	31,28%	30,95%	31,73%	29,70%	30,75%
	OECD	31,77%	28,70%	29,54%	29,58%	30,09%	28,71%	29,91%
School Inequity	Ireland	37,63%	59,29%	50,41%	41,41%	55,99%	56,94%	61,42%
	EU	45,51%	46,27%	43,99%	47,80%	47,53%	52,29%	53,53%
	OECD	38,58%	46,96%	42,60%	43,62%	44,23%	49,15%	50,32%

Figure 4 shows a relative stability in the correlation between performance and SES at student level at all three levels (OECD, EU and Ireland) especially from 2006 onwards.

Graph 4. Evolution of achievement-SES correlation at student level

Graph 5 shows that the levels of the correlation between achievement and SES at school level in the OECD and EU behave similarly to the previous graph. However, the evolution of Ireland is somewhat more variable, with a notable decline in 2009. Most of Ireland's scores are above .80, which indicate a large relationship between achievement and SES at school level.

Graph 5. Evolution of achievement-SES correlation at school level

Graph 6 shows the evolution of the degree of segregation of students in schools according to their SES. In the case of Ireland, no linear trend is observed, with the evolution being slightly upward until 2009, and then falling again between 2009 and 2018 to levels similar to those of 2000. Compared to the OECD and the EU, Ireland scores lower on this indicator.

Graph 6. Evolution of ICC SES (inequity due to SES distribution)

Graph 7 shows an evolution that is far from linear for School Inequity in the case of Ireland. The indicator rises sharply in 2003, reaching a score of 60%, which is considered a high level of inequity. It decreases from 2003 to 2009, when it gets to levels close to OECD and UE averages, but it rises again, and in 2018 it exceeds 60%.

Graph 7. Evolution of School Inequity (difficulty for social promotion through education)

Global score of the indicators

Table 3 provides data on global scores (average of the scores obtained 2000-2018) for each indicator, compared to EU and OECD averages.

Table 3. Evolution of equity indicators

		Ireland	EU	OECD
Equity as equal achievement	CV_{student}	16.53%	18,29%	18,15%
	CV_{school}	8.73%	13,78%	13,36%
	ICC_{achievement}	21.98%	44,59%	41,24%
Equity as equal opportunities	Rxy_{student}	0.38	0,40	0,39
	Rxy_{school}	0.79	0,67	0,66
	ICC_{SES}	23.20%	30,75%	29,72%
	School Inequity	51.87%	47,13%	45,21%

This information is also presented in graph form (graph 8). Ireland's scores are noticeably lower than OECD and EU averages in the three indicators related to equity as equal achievement, meaning that schools are not significantly different among them in terms of achievement averages, which is a positive and desirable thing in an education system. Regarding equity as equal opportunities indicators, while schools do not seem to be segregated according to student SES, both the relationship between achievement and SES at school level and the School Inequity indicator are above OECD and EU averages, indicating that equal opportunities for all students regardless of their SES are hindered to some extent.

Graph 8. Global equity scores